

Titrimetric Determination of Hydrogen Peroxide and Sodium Perborate by Periodate

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HUCKABA and Keyes¹ determined hydrogen peroxide with permanganate in acid medium. Willard and Young² obtained good results with ceric sulphate. Perborate reacts with potassium permanganate and ceric sulphate in the same way as hydrogen peroxide. Schwicker³ reduced periodate to iodate in alkaline medium with hydrogen peroxide. It has been observed in the present investigation that if periodate is taken in excess, hydrogen peroxide and sodium perborate are quantitatively oxidised.

Periodate can be selectively masked with molybdate whereas iodate remains unaffected⁴. The same masking effect has been utilised in the determination of iodate formed by periodate oxidation of hydrogen peroxide and sodium perborate (eq. 1 and 2). The reaction products in each case are treated with potassium iodide in presence of chloroacetic acid buffer after masking periodate with molybdate :

Since the iodate formed is stoichiometrically related to the amount of the substance taken, the liberated iodine can be represented by

The titration of the liberated iodine makes the method highly sensitive and suitable for the determination of small amounts of the substances.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of analytical grade commercially available. Solutions of hydrogen peroxide and sodium perborate were prepared by dissolving these substances, in distilled water and standardised iodometrically.

Buffer solution was prepared by dissolving 25 g of chloroacetic acid in 70 ml distilled water and its pH adjusted to 2.9 with a strong solution of sodium hydroxide.

2 M molybdate solution was prepared by dissolving ammonium molybdate in hot distilled water.

Procedure :

A suitable aliquot of the substance to be determined, was pipetted into an Erlenmeyer flask containing an excess of potassium metaperiodate (50-100

mg). The contents of the flask were shaken for 2-3 min and 10 ml of 2 M ammonium molybdate followed by 10 ml of chloroacetic acid buffer were added. 1 g of potassium iodide was then added and contents of the flask thoroughly mixed. The liberated iodine was titrated with 0.1 N sodium thiosulphate solution. The results are given in the Table. 1

TABLE 1 DETERMINATION OF HYDROGEN PEROXIDE AND SODIUM PERBORATE

Taken	Hydrogen Peroxide (mg)		Error
	Found		
4.72	4.70		-0.02
5.50	5.50		0.00
6.57	6.55		-0.02
7.08	7.08		0.00
7.99	8.02		+0.03
8.96	9.01		+0.05
	Sodium Perborate (mg)		
20.66	20.66		0.00
24.10	24.23		+0.13
27.54	27.54		0.00
31.52	31.37		-0.15
35.46	35.45		-0.01
39.40	39.53		+0.13

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Study of Cucumis melo utilissimus Seed Oil

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CUCUMIS MELO UTILISSIMUS Duthie and Fuller known as *Kakri* in hindi belongs to the family cucurbitaceae. Seeds are cooling, nutritious, diuretic and used in painful micturition and suppression of urine¹. It is cultivated in many parts of India, specially in upper India and particularly in Uttar Pradesh and Punjab². The present work deals with the chemical investigation of the seed oil of *Kakri* which has not been reported so far. Taking into account the medicinal use of the seed of the plant information on general characteristics and fatty acid

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composition is of utmost importance. The main objective of the work was to correlate the fatty acid composition and unsaponifiable matter in the seed oil to its medicinal uses.

Experimental :

Authentic samples of *Jaunpury Kakri* seeds were used in the present investigation. 600 g air dried seeds were broken by suitable methods. The oil content was determined in a continuous soxhlet extractor using petroleum ether (60-80) as solvent. This was purified by filtering through animal charcoal and drying over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The characteristics of the oil were determined by conventional methods. The results are presented in Table 1. 100 g oil were mixed with excess of alcoholic KOH and boiled for eight hours over a water bath. The alcohol was distilled off and the soap was dissolved in excess of water. The

TABLE-1 CHARACTERISTICS OF OIL SEEDS AND OIL

Moisture %	7.5
Oil %	32.00
Oil % (on kernel)	41.00
Colour of oil	Yellow
Refractive Index at 30°	1.4200
Specific gravity at 31°	0.902
Acid value	8.8
Saponification value	226.4
Saponification equivalent	247.8
Iodine value	94.2
Consistency	Liquid
U. M.	0.81%

unsaponifiable matter was separated by filtration. Then the soap solution was extracted with ether. This removed any remaining unsaponifiable matter. The soap solution was treated with dil. sulphuric acid and the mixture was heated for a few minutes. The liberated fatty acids were taken in a separating funnel after dissolving the fatty acids in ethyl ether. The ethereal solution of fatty acids was washed several times with water to free it from impurities. Ether was distilled off and a mixture of fatty acids obtained. The mixed fatty acids were separated into solid and liquid acids by Twithells Lead salt method modified by Hilditch.

The saponification and iodine values of the mixed fatty acids (Solid and Liquid) were determined separately and presented in a tabular form (Table 2).

TABLE-2 CHARACTERISTICS OF SOLID AND LIQUID FATTY ACIDS

	Solid fatty acids	Liquid fatty acids
%	22%	78%
Iodine value	22.5	98.0
Saponification value	242.2	212.6
Saponification equivalent	231.6	268.6

The quantitative and qualitative composition of the component acids of the mixed fatty acids are determined by methyl ester distillation, urea adduct fractionation and paper chromatographic methods.

TABLE-3 FRACTIONAL DISTILLATION OF SOLID FATTY ACID METHYL ESTERS

Total weight of esters = 12.2 g

Fractions	Distillation temp. in°C	Weight of acids in g	S.V. of acids	S.E. of acids	I.V. of acids
1	150-165	1.5	303.1	185.1	30.0
2	165-180	2.055	248.4	225.8	26.2
3	180-195	3.95	208.8	268.7	20.5
4	195 and above	3.06	203.5	275.6	30.2

Pressure = 10 mm.

TABLE-4 FRACTIONAL DISTILLATION OF LIQUID FATTY ACID METHYL ESTERS

Total weight of esters = 44.5 g

Fractions	Distillation temp. in°C	Weight of acids in g	S.V. of acids	S.E. of acids	I.V. of acids
1	150-160	4.725	202.0	277.7	80.1
2	160-170	8.62	201.1	278.9	114.8
3	170-180	15.40	201.2	278.8	123.1
4	180-and above	10.69	201.3	278.7	142.8

Pressure = 10 mm.

TABLE-5 FATTY ACID COMPOSITION OF THE OIL

Species	8:0	10:0	12:0	14:0	16:0	16:1	18:0	18:1	18:2
<i>Cucumis melo utilissimus</i>	1.2	0.8	2.0	0.91	13.1	0.73	3.96	44.1	33.2

Results and discussion

Cucumis melo utilissimus seed oil (32.00% on seed, 41.00% on kernel) is yellow in colour. The major fatty acid components of the oil are Oleic acid (44.1%) and Linoleic acid 33.2%. Palmitic and Stearic acids are present to the extent of 13.1% and 3.36% respectively. The other acids present are Caprylic 1.2%, Capric 0.8%, Lauric 2.00% and Myristic 0.91%. Hexadecenoic acid is present to the extent of 0.73%. High percentage of unsaturated acids is responsible for the cooling effect of seeds. It is the general characteristic of cucurbitaceae family.

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